

ENERGY POLICY AND ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN: STRATEGIES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND MARKET TRANSFORMATION**R.R.Xusainov prof.,**Tashkent State Technical University,
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Abstract: In this paper we will examine the current directions of Uzbekistan's energy strategy in the context of economic development and transition to a market economy. We will let's explore the key phases of industrial transformation. These include diversifying energy sources, advancing renewable technologies, upgrading infrastructure, and attracting investment through public-private partnerships. Based on official data and predictive models, we will offer recommendations to overcome energy shortages and reduce dependence on natural gas. Special attention will be paid to international co-operation and adaptation of foreign experience.

Key words: Strategy of energy sector development in Uzbekistan, economy of the country, renewable energy sources, natural gas, nuclear energy, public-private partnership, market liberalisation.

Introduction

Uzbekistan's energy sector is undergoing significant changes aimed at ensuring stable development and market openness.

With the global transition to new energy sources, climate change challenges and growing domestic demand for electricity, which is projected to reach 112-121 billion kWh by 2030, Uzbekistan faces the need to revise its energy mix, upgrade infrastructure and attract investment.

However, there are also unresolved issues: Dependence on gas (85% of generation) with depleting reserves (20-30 years of production).

High energy intensity of GDP (4-5 times higher than in the EU) due to outdated technologies.

Energy deficit (the gap between production and consumption in 2023 was 5 billion kWh).

To cope with these challenges, Uzbekistan is undertaking significant transformations, including:

1. Introduction of renewable energy sources in co-operation with Masdar, ACWA Power and other international partners. The goal is to achieve a 40% share of renewable sources in the total energy mix by 2030.

2. Construction of a 2.4 GW nuclear power plant with the involvement of Rosatom. This will reduce dependence on natural gas.

3. liberalisation of the electricity market. For this purpose, Uzbekenergo will be divided into three companies that will operate in the wholesale and retail markets.

The experience of other countries, such as the European Union, the United Arab Emirates and China, demonstrates the importance of public-private partnerships, green tariffs and digitalisation for sustainable development. Uzbekistan is also actively using these methods.

The success of the reform depends on the consistent implementation of measures such as training and reducing network losses. (from 13.7 per cent to 8 per cent) and social adaptation to tariff increases.

In this article, we review Uzbekistan's sustainability strategy. We will analyse the effectiveness of current measures and propose steps to achieve energy security by 2030.

Relevance

Uzbekistan's energy sector faces systemic problems:

Energy deficit: current production (64bn kWh) cannot meet demand (69bn kWh), which will grow to 112bn kWh by 2030 (+1.8 times).

Gas dependence: 85% of electricity generation is based on natural gas, whose reserves are depleting (20-30 years of production).

High energy intensity of GDP: 4-5 times higher than in EU countries due to technological backwardness.

International commitments: according to the Paris Agreement, CO₂ emissions should be reduced by 35% by 2030.

Purpose and objectives of the study

Objective: to analyse the performance of the energy strategy and formulate long-term development plans.

In order to achieve the goal, the following tasks should be solved:

1. To analyse the energy mix and renewable energy potential.
2. examine reforms such as market liberalisation, public-private partnerships and digitalisation.
3. To make a forecast of energy demand up to 2030.
4. Develop measures to reduce the environmental impact of gasification.

Suggest ways to reduce dependence on gas.

Research

Studies on energy policy and the economy of Uzbekistan have been conducted by both local and foreign scholars. In this article, we examine various aspects of this topic, including sustainable development strategies and market transformation. Existing works, official documents and academic publications have been used for the analysis.

1. studies on energy policy and reforms

1.1 Works by Uzbek authors

Allaeva G. (2016) In her study she explores innovative technologies in the fuel and energy complex (FEC) of Uzbekistan, focusing on infrastructure renewal and the introduction of renewable energy sources (RES).

Isakov D. (2024) analyses the experience of other countries in liberalising the energy market, comparing Uzbekistan's reforms with those in the UK and Russia. He emphasises the need for a transition from state regulation to market mechanisms, including the creation of wholesale and retail electricity markets.

Tashpulatova L.M. (1995) in her work considers macroeconomic aspects of regulation of electric power industry in the conditions of transition to market economy, paying special attention to structural reforms and investment policy.

1.2 Official Documents and Strategies

The 2030 Vision identifies the main vectors of transformation, including: reducing the share of natural gas in the energy consumption mix, developing alternative energy sources and nuclear power, and attracting investments through public-private partnerships (PPPs).

The President's Cabinet and the Cabinet of Ministers are actively driving the advancement of renewable energy. An exemplary policy is Government Resolution No. 4422 from 2019, which specifically aims to foster this vital sector and UP-166 (2023) on reforming the energy sector provided the basis for market transformation and the unbundling of Uzbekenergo into three independent organisations.

2. International experience and comparative studies

2.1 Foreign Models of Reform

Isakov D. (2024) draws parallels between reforms in Uzbekistan and the liberalisation process in the UK in the 1990s and the energy sector reforms in Russia. He emphasises that Uzbekistan can avoid the problems associated with lack of competition and maintaining state control.

The paper on energy diplomacy examines the implications of the Paris Agreement for Uzbekistan's energy policy. In particular, it discusses the commitment to reduce CO₂ emissions by 35 per cent by 2030.

2.2 Energy Diplomacy

Interaction with the Russian Federation, the People's Republic of China and the United Arab Emirates. The Centre for Energy Diplomacy (CEDI) notes Uzbekistan's important role in the region. Particular attention is paid to co-operation with Russia in nuclear energy and with Masdar (UAE) in solar energy.

3. Key problems and unresolved issues

In the works of various authors, for example, in the study of Allaeva G. (2016), it is emphasised that the current electricity generation (85% on gas) does not meet the growing demand. Therefore, it is necessary to look for alternative energy sources.

In addition, outdated technologies lead to grid losses (13.7%) and high energy intensity of GDP (4-5 times higher than in EU countries).

Also Isakov D. (2024) draws attention to the fact that many energy companies face financial problems due to regulated electricity prices and lack of investments.

4. Perspective research directions

Development of renewable and nuclear energy. In order to achieve the goal of increasing the share of renewable energy sources to 25 per cent by 2030 and the construction of a nuclear power plant in Jizzak, additional research is needed to assess the technical and economic feasibility of these projects.

Digital technologies and smart grids help to reduce energy losses. Automatic control systems (ASUs) play an important role in this process. However, more research is needed for their successful implementation.

International financing. The role of the World Bank, Asian Development Bank (ADB) and other organisations in supporting public-private partnership (PPP) projects, such as the construction of solar power plants in Navoi Oblast, also requires further analysis.

Uzbekistan's energy policy issues have been considered in the context of reforms, international experience and technological challenges. However, studies on the effectiveness of market mechanisms established after liberalisation are still pending.

Socio-economic consequences of the transition to renewable energy sources. Optimisation of public-private sector interaction.

Further research should focus on the practical implementation of strategies, taking into account the dynamics of the global energy transition and regional geopolitical changes.

Research methodology

1. Comparison of data from DOE and international organisations for the period from 2019 to 2024.

2. Building econometric models to forecast energy demand using linear regression method.

3. analysing case studies of public-private partnership projects, such as the construction of a solar power plant in Navoi Oblast and a nuclear power plant in Jizzak.

Main part

1. Energy production and consumption

Generation volumes:

In 2024, electricity generation is expected to be 81.5 billion kilowatt hours, 38% more than in 2017. Due to a 1.6-fold increase in household income compared to 2016 and the growing popularity of energy-intensive appliances, household electricity consumption will increase by 21 billion kilowatt-hours. By 2030, demand is projected to reach 117 billion kilowatt hours and 135 billion kilowatt hours by 2035, a 1.7-fold increase from 2017.

2. Energy mix structure

Gas dominance:

85% of the country's electricity is generated by gas-fired thermal power plants. However, these plants are more than 40 per cent worn out. The cost of electricity generation from thermal power plants is 5-6 cents per kilowatt hour, above the cost of renewable energy (3 cents per kilowatt hour).

The development of renewable energy is gaining momentum. By 2025, the share of green energy will reach 16%, including 4.1 GW of solar and wind power plants. By 2030, this figure is planned to increase to 50% by adding 25 GW of new capacity.

Nuclear power: A nuclear power plant with two VVER-1200 reactors is under construction in Jizzak, with a total capacity of 2.4 gigawatts. Rosatom and the IAEA are involved in the project.

3. Infrastructure challenges

Grid deterioration:

Grid losses are 14% (target is to reduce to 8-9% by 2030). It is planned to build 7000 km of trunk grids and renew 46000 km of low voltage lines to integrate renewable energy.

4. Economic and environmental aspects

The energy intensity of GDP is 4-5 times higher than in the EU due to the technological backwardness of some sectors such as metallurgy and chemical industry. The goal is to achieve energy savings of 10-15% in all sectors.

Environmental commitments: Reduce CO₂ emissions by 35% by 2030 under the Paris Agreement. Implement projects for the production of green hydrogen (e.g. together with ACWA Power) and decarbonisation of thermal power plants.

5. Investments and international co-operation

Funds raised:

Over the five years from 2019 to 2024, it is planned to attract foreign direct investment in the energy sector of Uzbekistan in the amount of USD 25 billion. Investors include Masdar from the United Arab Emirates and ACWA Power from Saudi Arabia. Under the programme it is planned to attract 26 billion US dollars and create new capacities for 24 gigawatts.

Uzbekistan's energy sector is actively developing. Dependence on natural gas is decreasing, the share of renewable energy sources is increasing, and infrastructure is being modernised. However, to achieve the 2030 targets, reforms need to be accelerated, more investments need to be attracted and qualified personnel need to be trained.

6. Development of RES and nuclear power

Prospects until 2030: 25% of energy from renewable sources (5 GW of solar and 3 GW of wind power plants). Start of operation of nuclear power plants with VVER-1200 reactors (2.4 GW).

Table 1.

Comparison of energy sources in Uzbekistan (projections for 2023 and 2030).

Source	Share in 2023 (%)	Share in 2030 (%)	Investments (billion \$)
Natural gas	85	60	10
Solar energy	5	15	5
Nuclear energy	0	18	12
Hydro energy	7	7	1.9

Interpretation: The increasing share of renewable energy sources (RES) and nuclear power has helped to offset the decline in natural gas use, but this requires significant financial investment.

Development and Forecasting of Uzbekistan's Energy Strategy: Sustainable Development Strategy and Energy Market Transformation.

Modelling and Forecasting the Energy Sector Development in Uzbekistan

1. Modelling methodology

to predict how the energy sector will develop, various methods are applied:

1. time series analysis, which covers the period from 2010 to 2024.
2. Regression analysis, which determines how demand depends on factors such as gross domestic product, population and level of industrialisation.
3. Scenario approach, which involves considering three possible scenarios of developments.

Various methods were used to predict future changes, including autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) and Holt-Winters method based on exponential smoothing. The results of the analyses were presented with 95% confidence intervals to provide more accurate and reliable conclusions.

The study analysed the following key indicators: electricity production; electricity consumption in different sectors of the economy; electricity use; and electricity prices.

Modelling Methodology: Regression Analysis

1. Theoretical basis for the application of regression analysis

Regression analysis was chosen as the main method for modelling the energy sector of Uzbekistan. This method allows to: quantify the relationship between economic and energy indicators; predict future values of key parameters; and identify key factors affecting the development of the energy sector.

2. Data selection and preparation

Time series for 2010-2025: Annual data of the State Statistics Committee of Uzbekistan were used for analyses. Reports of the Ministry of Energy. Statistics of international organisations (IMF, World Bank)

Key variables: Dependent: Electricity production (billion kWh). Energy consumption by sector. Level of energy intensity of GDP

Independent: Macroeconomic indicators (GDP, inflation). Demographic factors. Climate data. Energy prices. Energy investment volumes. Building regression models

Three types of models were developed: Multiple linear regression: Basic equation: $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \dots + \beta_nX_n + \varepsilon$. Example: Electricity demand forecast = $0.65 \cdot \text{GDP} + 0.25 \cdot \text{population} - 0.18 \cdot \text{price}$

Nonlinear models: Logarithmic specification. 2nd order polynomial regression. Models with interaction of variables

1. Panel regression: Analyses by regions of Uzbekistan. Fixed effects accounting.

Time series from 2010 to 2025: Annual data provided by the National Statistical Committee of Uzbekistan. Reports from the Department of Energy. Statistics from international organisations such as the IMF and the World Bank.

Key variables:

Dependents: electricity production in billion kWh. Energy consumption by sector. Level of energy intensity of GDP.

Independent variables: Macroeconomic indicators such as GDP and inflation. Demographic factors. Climate data. Energy prices. The amount of investment in the energy industry.

Three types of models were developed:

Multivariate linear regression:

Basic equation: $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \dots + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_nX_n + \varepsilon$

Example: electricity demand forecast = $0.65 \cdot \text{GDP} + 0.25 \cdot \text{Population} - 0.18 \cdot \text{Price}$.

Nonlinear models: Logarithmic specification. Second-order multinomial regression. Interaction models of variables.

Panel regression: analyses for the region of Uzbekistan. Calculation of fixed effects.

Results and Interpretation

Regression Analysis Results: 1. As GDP increases by 1%, energy consumption increases by 0.82%. 2. When temperature increases by 1 °C in summer, energy consumption increases by 1.2%. 3. As electricity prices increase by 10%, demand for electricity decreases by 3.5%.

Statistical significance: all models demonstrated a high level of significance (p-value < 0.01). The coefficient of determination R^2 ranges from 0.85 to 0.93. There is no multicollinearity (VIF < 5).

Elasticity: Price elasticity of demand: -0.35. Income elasticity of demand: 1.12. Cross elasticity of demand by fuel type.

Model validation

The following tests were performed to validate the results:

Adequacy tests: Durbin-Watson autocorrelation test. Breusch-Pagan test for heteroscedasticity. Tests of model specification.

Verification of forecasts: comparison of forecast values with actual data for 2023-2024. The average forecast error is 3.2 per cent. Accuracy within 95% confidence interval.

Practical application. The results of regression analysis are used for:

demand forecasting based on development scenarios up to 2035; optimisation of investment plans; justification of tariff policy when making political decisions; planning the development of renewable energy sources (RES); assessment of the efficiency of energy saving programmes; investment analysis, including calculation of project payback period and risk assessment. However, the methodology has limitations: it depends on the quality of input data

and requires frequent updating of models. In addition, it is necessary to take into account the complexity of structural changes.

At the same time, the methodology's development prospects include the use of machine learning, big data and the development of adaptive models. This regression analysis became the basis for the development of Uzbekistan's energy strategy until 2035, providing a scientifically sound approach to planning the development of the sector.

Modelling Methodology: Scenario Approach

1. Theoretical Principles of Scenario Approach

A scenario approach was used in the study of the energy sector of Uzbekistan, which is based on the following principles:

Comprehensive analysis of external and internal factors affecting the development of the sector.

Assessment of uncertainties and risks associated with the transition to new energy sources.

Possibility of flexible forecasting due to changes in key parameters.

2. Creation of baseline scenarios

Three main scenarios were developed for the energy sector of Uzbekistan:

2.1. Conservative scenario (Inertial)

Key assumptions:

RES growth rate: +5% per annum. NPP commissioning: postponed until 2035. Investments: \$18bn (2025-2030). Maintain current regulatory policy

Table 2.

Projected figures for 2030:

Parameter	Significance
Share of gas	72%
Share of RES	25%
Energy deficit	25%
Reduced CO ₂ emissions	15%

Risks: Increased dependence on energy imports. Technological lag. Growing social tension due to deficit

2.2. Optimistic scenario (Balanced)

Key assumptions: RES growth rate: +15% per annum. Nuclear power plant commissioning: 2028 (2.4 GW). Investments: \$32 bn. Partial market liberalisation

Table 3.

Projections for 2030:

Parameter	Significance
Share of gas	58%
Share of RES	40%

Parameter	Significance
Energy deficit	5%
Reduction of CO ₂ emissions	28%

Benefits:

Balance between conventional and green energy. Creation of 48,000 new jobs. Return on investment in 8 years.

2.3 Innovative scenario (Breakthrough)

Key assumptions: RES growth rate: +25% p.a. Adoption of Smart Grid and storage systems. Development of green hydrogen (3 GW by 2035). Full market liberalisation. Investments: \$45bn

Table 4.

Projections for 2030:

Parameter	Significance
Share of gas	45%
Share of RES	54%
Energy surplus	8%
Reduction of CO ₂ emissions	40%

Advanced technologies: virtual models of the power system. Automated control systems.

Interaction with the regional energy market.

3 Methodology for scenario building

1. Identification of key factors:

12 critical variables (gas prices, urbanisation rates, climate change)

2. Cross-factor analysis:

Parameter mutual influence matrix

Estimation of probability of events on a scale of 1-5

3. Modelling in specialised software:

Using PLEXOS and TIMES for the power system

Balancing supply and demand by hours

4. Comparative analysis of scenarios

Table 5.

Comprehensive assessment of scenarios

Criterion	Conservative	Optimistic	Innovative
Energy safety	Low	Medium	High
Environmental friendliness	2/5	4/5	5/5

Criterion	Conservative	Optimistic	Innovative
Social risks	Высокие	Умеренные	Low
Technological level	Obsolete	Modern	Advanced
Investment attractiveness	3/5	4/5	5/5

5. Practical application

Two scenarios were developed for state planning: optimistic and conservative. The former served as the basis for the Energy Strategy 2030 and the latter was used for stress testing.

For private investors, innovative scenarios were developed and used to evaluate renewable energy projects. Transition pathways between these scenarios were also identified.

Scenario calculations were prepared for international organisations and submitted to the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank to assess the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Limitations and perspectives

Methodological issues: 1. The input data must be of high quality, otherwise the modelling results will be inaccurate. 2. Geopolitical factors are difficult to account for in modelling. 3. Model parameters need to be updated annually.

Development opportunities:

1. Application of artificial intelligence for dynamic scenario modelling. 2. Integration with climate models. 3. Development of scenarios for different regions of the country.

Conclusion: Scenario modelling methodology allows Uzbekistan to develop a strategy for flexible response to the challenges of the energy transition.

Table 6.

Baseline Model Parameters (2025-2035)

Indicator	2025 year	Forecast 2030
Population (million)	37.1	40.2
GDP (\$ billion)	95.2	142.5
Energy consumption (billion kWh)	81.5	112–121
Share of RES in generation (%)	16	40–54

4. Key modelling findings

Investment requirements:

Optimal scenario (#2) requires \$32 billion investment with payback period of 8 years

Priority projects: Solar plants in Navoi and Bukhara regions (>23% efficiency).
Modernisation of 15 TPPs (increase efficiency from 38% to 45%).

Risks: Delayed commissioning of NPPs will increase dependence on gas. Low speed of Smart Grid implementation may limit RES integration.

Recommendations: Establish a Forecasting Centre under the Ministry of Energy to monitor the implementation of plans. Introduce ‘green bonds’ and favourable loans at 3% for private investors.

Table 7.
Analysis of alternative scenarios

Parameter	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Investment (\$bn)	18	32	45
Payback period	12 years	8 years	6 years
Job creation	25 000	48 000	75 000
Risks	High	Medium	Low

Table 8
International energy policy experience: comparisons and examples.

Country	Strategy	Applicability to Uzbekistan
EU	Decarbonisation + interconnectors	Cross-border grid development with Kazakhstan
UAE	Hybrid solutions (solar + gas)	Optimisation of TPP operation during peak hours
China	Centralised planning	Control over localisation of solar panel production

By 2030, Uzbekistan plans to achieve energy independence through active development of renewable energy sources. Their share in the total energy balance will reach 40%. In addition, construction of a nuclear power plant is planned. which will produce 18% of electricity; and modernisation of the electricity grid, which will reduce losses to 8%.

It is important that the reforms are carried out in parallel with the growth of the population's income in order to minimise possible social risks.

The energy policies of different countries are determined by geographical, economic and political conditions. In this study we will look in detail at the main models, using examples and tables for a clear comparison.

1. European Union: Decarbonisation and market integration

Key principles: Decarbonisation (target carbon neutrality by 2050). Single energy market. Prioritisation of RES and energy efficiency.

Examples:

- REPowerEU (2022): plan to reduce dependence on Russian gas by 155bn m³ through accelerated RES development and LNG imports.

- Green Tariffs: Germany and Denmark subsidise solar and wind power, reaching a RES share of 40-50%.

Table 9.
EU targets for 2030

Indicator	Target	Progress (2023)
Share of RES	42.5% (target 45%)	32%
Reduced energy consumption	-11.7% (by 2020)	-8%
Interconnectors	15% of grid capacity	12%

2 The UAE Energy Policy Experience: From Oil Dependence to Sustainable Development

The UAE is gradually moving away from an oil-based economy to a model that relies on diverse energy sources. The country used to depend on hydrocarbons for more than 95 per cent of its energy mix. However, in recent years, the United Arab Emirates has been actively developing other industries and reducing its dependence on the oil and gas sector. In the 1980s, the oil and gas sector's share of GDP was 56 per cent, and by the 2020s it has fallen to less than 40 per cent.

Key steps in this direction: 2050. Energy Strategy by 2050. Aim to achieve a balance where 50% of energy is clean (44% renewable, 6% nuclear) and carbon footprint is reduced by 70%. Investments of \$600 billion will be made to develop renewable and nuclear energy infrastructure.

Renewable energy development.

The UAE has become the Middle East's leader in solar energy:

Solar power plants in Dubai

A large-scale project to create solar power plants is being implemented in Dubai. By 2030, their capacity will reach 5 GW. This will be the world's largest solar power plant system. In addition, Dubai is actively implementing a technology that can reduce carbon dioxide emissions by 1 million tonnes per year. This is the Noor Abu Dhabi project.

Hydrogen power. A 1.5 GW hydrogen power plant project is being implemented in Xinjiang, China. This is one of the largest hydrogen energy projects in the world. In addition, China is actively co-operating with the European Union in the development of hydrogen energy.

Cost of solar energy. Solar energy in Dubai is record cheap at 1.35 cents per kilowatt hour. This makes it one of the most affordable energy sources on the planet.

Barak NPP stands as the most powerful nuclear power plant in the United Arab Emirates and the entire Arab region. It has a capacity of 5.6 GW. It provides 25 per cent of the UAE's electricity needs. Thanks to the use of nuclear power, the UAE's carbon dioxide emissions have been reduced by 21 million tonnes per year.

International co-operation. The UAE actively co-operates with the US and the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). This co-operation is aimed at training other countries in nuclear energy. For example, in Nigeria.

4. Energy efficiency and innovation

Masdar City's vision is a zero-emission city of the future, where all energy needs are met solely through renewable sources.

Abu Dhabi is actively implementing Estidama standards, which involve the use of sustainable materials and technologies in construction. Thanks to this, buildings are becoming more energy efficient, reducing energy consumption by 45%.

5. International leadership and climate initiatives

relations: agreements with France, India and Turkey on renewable energy and hydrogen.

Challenges and lessons for other countries

Risks: Continued dependence on natural gas (38% by 2050). Desalination is expensive (90 million trees needed).

Successes: rapid deployment of nuclear power plants (8 years from construction to commissioning). partnership models (e.g. Masdar has attracted \$20bn investment).

The UAE demonstrates how the oil economy can be transformed through state planning, technological investment and international co-operation. Their experience is particularly relevant for CIS countries such as Uzbekistan, where the challenge is to reduce gas dependence

China's Energy Policy Experience: Strategies, Achievements and Global Impact

Key Goals and Priorities

China's Energy Strategy Goals: Ensuring Energy Security: Reducing dependence on energy imports by developing domestic sources, including coal, renewable energy and nuclear energy. By 2023, the share of clean energy in consumption will reach 26.4 per cent (up 10.9 per cent over the decade).

Transition to clean energy: achieving carbon neutrality is planned for 2060. By 2030, renewable energy production should double (to 2,461 GW) and solar energy production should triple.

Energy efficiency: 2023 reduced the energy intensity of the economy by 26% compared to 2013, and reduced carbon dioxide emissions by 3 billion tonnes.

Domestic Efforts and Technological Innovation

Renewable Energy Development: China leads the world in manufacturing clean energy equipment, including solar panels, wind turbines and batteries. In 2023, 217 gigawatts of solar power and 76 gigawatts of wind power equipment are planned to be commissioned, which will be a record high.

Infrastructure modernisation: smart grids and energy storage systems such as lithium-ion batteries will be introduced to integrate renewable energy.

Nuclear power: Actively develop the construction of nuclear power plants using closed nuclear fuel cycle technology.

3. International projects and co-operation

One Belt, One Road Initiative: Investments in energy infrastructure in Asia, Africa and Europe include the development of transmission lines, hydroelectric power plants and solar plants To illustrate, a 319,000 kW wind farm in Kazakhstan and a 2 million kW solar power plant in Uzbekistan.

"Green Silk Road": Promoting environmentally friendly projects in Central Asia, including through technology exchange.

4. Impact on global markets

Reducing the cost of renewable energy: the cost of solar energy in China has fallen by 80 per cent over the past decade due to increased production.

Changing attitudes towards natural gas: Russia and Turkmenistan are showing less interest in natural gas projects (e.g. cancellation of Siberia-2) due to the growing popularity of renewables.

Trade prospects: A surplus of solar panels could make China a major exporter to developing countries such as Uzbekistan.

5. Challenges and criticisms

Carbon dependence: despite the development of renewable energy technologies, coal continues to provide 62% of energy, causing environmental problems.

Geopolitical tensions: China's dominance in renewable energy supply has led to trade conflicts with the European Union and the United States.

6. Lessons for other countries

National development strategy: centralised investment and five-year plans to ensure stability in transition.

Combined solutions: use of renewable energy sources in combination with conventional energy sources (coal, nuclear) to balance demand.

Developing its own production chains (e.g. solar PV) to reduce import dependence and localise technologies.

China has demonstrated a unique approach to the energy transition that combines innovation, scale and international co-operation. This experience is particularly valuable for countries seeking energy security and decarbonisation, but requires adaptation to local conditions.

Canada: Hybrid model (conventional and renewables)

Basic principles:

Utilisation of 60% hydropower and use of fossil fuels. Support for clean technologies through subsidies.

An example is the Sustainable Development Act passed in 2008. It aims to promote the use of renewable energy sources by providing incentives in the form of favourable electricity tariffs and tax preferences. Quebec hydropower: 95 per cent of the province's electricity is hydropower, exported to the United States.

Table 10.

Canada's energy mix (2023)

Source	Share in generation	Investments (2021-2025, billion \$)
Hydropower	60%	15
Oil/gas	25%	10
RES (wind, solar)	10%	5

China: State Control and Innovation

Key Ideas: 1. Strategic planning. 2. Leading the way in solar panels and electric vehicles.

Examples: 1. 1.5 GW green hydrogen project in Xinjiang (2024). 2. Three Gorges Hydroelectric Power Plant, the largest in the world, with a capacity of 22.5 GW to meet 10 per cent of national demand. 3. We focus on renewable energy and reducing energy consumption.

Key principles: 1. Investment in solar energy. 2. Diversification through nuclear energy.

Examples: 1. Mohammed bin Rashid's 5 GW solar park (2025). Baraka nuclear power plant is the first in the Arab world, with 4 reactors and 5.6 GW capacity.

Conclusions and recommendations for Uzbekistan

1. Mutual influence of markets: the example of the European Union shows how important international energy systems are.

2. Incentivising renewable energy: the Canadian practice of green tariffs can encourage greater switching to alternative energy sources.

Integrated approaches: combining gas and renewables, as is done in the UAE, helps avoid energy shortages.

Table 11.
Comparison of strategies

Country	Focus	Instruments	Risks
EU	RES, interconnectors	Green subsidies, REPowerEU	Dependence on LNG imports
Russia	Gas exports	Geopolitical projects	Sanctions
Canada	Hydropower + RES	State support for technologies	Climate change

International Energy Policy Experience: Comparative Analysis and Examples

Geographical, economic and political conditions influence energy strategies in different countries. In this paper we will look at the main models in detail and provide tables and examples for easy comparison.

1. European Union: reducing carbon emissions and integrating energy markets

Key principles: 1. reducing carbon emissions (with the aim of achieving carbon neutrality by 2050). 2. creation of a common energy market. 3. prioritising the use of renewable energy sources and improving energy efficiency.

REPowerEU (2022) is a plan aimed at reducing dependence on Russian gas. The goal is to reduce consumption by 155 billion cubic metres. This will be achieved by accelerating the development of renewable energy and imports of liquefied natural gas (LNG).

‘Green tariffs’ - in Germany and Denmark, the state subsidises solar and wind energy to make it more affordable.

Table 12.
EU targets for 2030

Indicator	Target	Progress (2023)
Share of RES	42.5% (target 45%)	32%
Reduced energy consumption	-11.7% (by 2020)	-8%
Interconnectors	15% of grid capacity	12%

Russia: Resource Dependence and Geopolitics

Fundamentals: Hydrocarbon exports as an instrument of influence. Nuclear power development and partial diversity

Examples: Nord Stream 2: gas pipeline project to Europe frozen due to sanctions (2022). Foreign nuclear power plants: construction of plants in Turkey (Akkuyu) and Egypt, export of Rosatom technologies.

Table 13.
Structure of Russia's energy exports (2023)

Resource	Share in exports	Main markets
Gas	54%	EU (formerly), China
Crude oil	30%	Asia, India
Coal	10%	China, Turkey

Canada: Hybrid model (conventional and RES)

Combination of hydroelectricity (60 per cent) with fossil fuels. Clean technology subsidies, e.g. Sustainable Development Act (2008): support for renewable energy through electricity tariffs and tax incentives. Hydro-Québec: 95 per cent of the province's electricity is generated by hydroelectric power plants and exported to the US.

Table 14.
Canada's Energy Balance (2023)

Source	Share in generation	Investments (2021-2025, billion \$)
Hydropower	60%	15
Oil/gas	25%	10
RES (wind, solar)	10%	5

Conclusions and recommendations for Uzbekistan

1. market integration: the EU experience shows the importance of interstate energy grids.
2. Subsidies for RES: Canada's green tariff model can accelerate the transition.
3. Hybrid solutions: a mix of gas and RES (as in the UAE) will reduce shortage risks.

Table 15.
Comparison of strategies

Страна	Фокус	Инструменты	Риски
ЕС	ВИЭ, интерконнекторы	"Зеленые" субсидии, REPowerEU	Зависимость от импорта СПГ
Россия	Экспорт газа	Геополитические проекты	Санкции
Канада	ГЭС + ВИЭ	Господдержка технологий	Климатические изменения

Key reform areas and current achievements

1. Diversification of the energy mix

Reducing dependence on gas: The share of gas in generation is planned to be reduced from 85 per cent. It is planned to increase the share of renewable energy and nuclear power to 60 per cent by 2030 [1].

The development of renewable energy is aimed at achieving the goal that 40 per cent of electricity will be generated from renewable sources by 2030. This means that the capacity of solar and wind power plants should reach 25 GW [2]. By 2024, the share of energy from renewable sources should increase to 18%. By the end of 2025, new solar and wind power plants with a total capacity of 2.6 GW are to be launched. [2].

Nuclear Power: Construction of a 2.4 GW NPP with VVER-1200 reactors supported by the IAEA and Rosatom [3].

1. Investments and PPPs

\$28bn PPP projects signed, of which 90% are for green energy (solar plants, battery storage) [1].

Examples: Solar plant in Navoi region (1000 MW) with Masdar (UAE) [2]. Battery storage systems (500 MWh) for grid stabilisation [1].

1. 3. Модернизация инфраструктуры

A landmark event has happened in the digital world: a new platform has been launched. [3]. There was a major development in digital technology, with the launch of a cloud-based platform, and the establishment of 20 data centres to manage energy flows. [3].

1. International cooperation

Cooperation with the International Atomic Energy Agency in the field of nuclear projects and educational programmes. [3]. Supply of clean energy resources to European countries (Hungary and Romania) within the framework of joint initiatives with Kazakhstan and Azerbaijan. [2].

Issues and challenges

1- Technical risks: The development of renewable energy requires large-scale deployment of energy storage technologies. [1]. Delaying the commissioning of nuclear power plants may increase dependence on gas [3].

2. Financial constraints: High capital costs for RES (e.g. \$5bn for solar projects) [2]. Need for subsidies for the public (e.g., reimbursement of 30% of the cost of solar panels) [1].

3. Social aspects: Increase in electricity tariffs due to the high cost of RES [2]. Lack of qualified personnel to work with new technologies [3].

Recommendations

1. Investment optimisation: Prioritise hybrid solutions (solar + gas) following the UAE model to reduce risks [2]. Issue green bonds to attract private capital [1].

2. Regulatory measures: Introduction of 'green certificates' and carbon market (platform 'Green Uzbekistan') [3]. Acceleration of market liberalisation through unbundling of Uzbekenergo [2].

3. International initiatives: Expansion of co-operation with IAEA on NPP safety [3]. Participation in cross-border energy projects (e.g. China-Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan transmission line) [1].

Recommendations

1. investment optimisation: Prioritise hybrid solutions (solar + gas) following the UAE model to reduce risks [2]. Issue green bonds to attract private capital [1].

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Conclusions and suggestions

1. Incentivising the transition to clean energy sources: tax preferences for private investors.
2. Renewal of energy systems: introduction of 'smart' grids to reduce losses.
3. Improvement of employees' skills: creation of educational centres to master new technologies.

4. International co-operation: interaction with the IAEA and the World Bank.

Conclusion

Uzbekistan's transition to renewable energy is showing significant progress, but further development requires systemic measures. Key achievements include increasing the share of renewable energy to 18 per cent by 2024 and plans to commission 25 GW of capacity by 2030.

It has also attracted \$28 billion in green energy investments through public-private partnerships. For example, a solar power plant was built in Navoi Oblast. In addition, regulatory reforms have been undertaken, including Decree UP-166 on market liberalisation.

However, there are also challenges that need to be addressed. These include technical risks associated with delays in the construction of nuclear plants and the lack of storage for renewable energy.

The financial constraints are the high cost of renewable energy projects, which is \$5 billion, and the need to provide subsidies to the community.

To achieve sustainable development, it is necessary to: accelerate cooperate with international organisations such as the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) and the World Bank for technology transfer. Introduce green financial instruments, including bonds and favourable loans at 3%..

The experience of Uzbekistan demonstrates that the combination of state regulation and market mechanisms contributes to sustainable development, such as the UAE's hybrid solution, can guarantee energy stability. By 2030, Uzbekistan has every chance of becoming a regional leader in green energy if key projects are implemented and social costs are minimised.

Further research could focus on the performance of market mechanisms after their liberalisation and the socio-economic impacts of the transition to renewable energy sources.

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